

PROPERTIES OF CENTAURIUM ERYTHREA IN THE TREATMENT OF DISEASES OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT

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Abstract

Nowadays, despite the active development of traditional medicine, the demand for herbal medicinals is constantly growing in the world. About 80% of the Earth's population use them for medicinal purposes. On the other hand, the use of medicinal plants in the future may be significantly limited due to the problem of decreasing biodiversity. This indicates the urgency of developing issues related not only to the effective medicinal use of plants with healing properties, but also to ensuring their protection and sustainable and long-term functioning of the population. Solving this issue, in turn, requires thorough research aimed at studying the state of leading medicinal plants in different regions and conditions of local growth

Keywords: aromatic plants, biochemical characteristics, centaurium erythrea.

Introduction. Centaurium erythraea Rafn. a medicinal plant that is actively used not only on the territory of Ukraine, but also on the territory of Serbia, Algeria, Italy, Morocco, Spain, Portugal. The plant is widely used in medicine due to its antipyretic, antidiabetic, antioxidant, detoxifying, anticoagulant, choleric, antitumor, hypotensive effects. [1,2]

Seven species of Centaurium Hill plants grow in Ukraine. [3] In scientific medicine, mainly two species are used: *S. erythraea* and *S. pulhellum* (Sw.) Druce, other species are not officially considered medicinal [4,5], most of them have a limited range and the possibility of their collection is limited [6].

Research materials and methods. The research material is the introduction of *Centaurium erythraea*, evaluation of its composition and pharmacological properties in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract.

Research results of pharmacological properties and applications. The herb contains glycosides (erythrocentaurine, gentsiopictin, erythaurine), alkaloids (erythrine, gentianine), essential oil, ascorbic and oleanolic acids, phytosterols, resins, flavonoids (luteolin, rutin, kaempferol, cosmozein, apigenin, apigenin, quercetin, etc.).

Centaurium erythraea grass contains essential oils (approximately 0.08-0.2%), which contain: citral (50%), geraniol (30%), nerol (7%), citronellol (4%), thymol (0.2%), lemon, sesquiterpene and other active substances [7]

Centaurium erythraea stimulates the secretion of the glands of the digestive tract, increases bile secretion, strengthens the peristalsis of the intestines and the contraction of the muscles of the uterus, exhibits anti-inflammatory, analgesic, weak laxative and anthelmintic effects. In scientific medicine, *Centaurium erythraea* is used as a means to stimulate appetite, improve diges-

tion, and increase peristalsis of the intestines. An infusion of *Centaurium erythraea* shows therapeutic activity in hypacid gastritis, some dyspepsia, flatulence, diseases of the liver, gall bladder and kidneys, and worms. In obstetrics and gynecology, preparations of golden-seal are prescribed to accelerate the contraction of the uterus in the postpartum period, to stop uterine bleeding after abortion, and for inflammatory diseases of the female genital organs. Herb tincture on Provençal oil is used to treat leg ulcers (*Ulcus cruris*). *Centaurium erythraea* is used as a folk remedy for reduced appetite, indigestion, especially for increased acidity of gastric juice, heartburn, flatulence, gastric bleeding and for diseases of the liver, biliary tract and kidneys, for hemorrhoids, tuberculosis of the lungs and peripheral lymph nodes, diabetes and diseases of the skin, against alcoholism, to restore strength after illnesses with a long, severe febrile state and with the flu. The *Centaurium erythraea* herb is part of teas to increase appetite, stomach teas, and bitter tincture, for the preparation of which take 60 parts of the herb 3. m., 60 parts of the leaves of the three-leaved mullein, 30 parts of the rhizome of the cane ayru, 30 parts of the bitter wormwood herb, 15 parts of the peel from tangerine fruits and 40% alcohol in such an amount that it is possible to make 1 liter of tincture. *Centaurium erythraea* improves the structural and functional properties of pancreatic cells by correcting endogenous antioxidant regulatory mechanisms and stimulating proliferative pathways in pancreatic beta cells.

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ANALYSIS OF BLOOD LIPID SPECTRUM INDICATORS IN CHRONIC PANCREATITIS COMBINED WITH HYPOTHYROIDISM

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Abstract

The study discusses futures of the plasma lipid profile (total cholesterol, triglycerides, low density lipoproteins, high density lipoproteins) and the peculiarities of their changes dynamic's in patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism comorbidity. The study of these pathologies comorbidity is rather promising area of clinical gastroenterology and endocrinology. Study revealed the most pronounced signs of dyslipidaemia in the group of patients with chronic pancreatitis and hypothyroidism. It confirms close pathogenetic relationship between these pathologies and requires further correction of treatment. Results indicates more comprehensive study of the course and interactions of these diseases in order to avoid complications and disability are needed.

Keywords: chronic pancreatitis, hypothyroidism, total cholesterol, triglycerides, low density lipoproteins, high density lipoproteins.

Introduction

Despite numerous studies, diseases of the pancreas, as a rule, are difficult to diagnose and treat. Nowadays, the mortality from acute pancreatitis remains high, the diagnosis of chronic pancreatitis in the early stages is a special test for the doctor, and its treatment is very often unsuccessful.[1] After all, for many years the pancreas has remained a mysterious and incomprehensible organ for doctors of various specialties: therapists, gastroenterologists, surgeons, oncologists, geneticists, etc.[2]

According to existing modern data, the function of the pancreas is under the influence of a whole series of hormones, and thyroid hormones occupy a special, regulatory place in this series. Thyroid hormones have a multifaceted effect on the body, influencing all organ systems and metabolism as a whole [3]. Deficiency of thyroid hormones leads to disorders on the part of organs and systems - cardiovascular, respiratory, digestive organs, etc. The state of the pancreas in hypothyroidism remains the least studied in gastroenterology,

although B.L. Baker and E.S. Pliske in 1957 pointed out that when the thyroid gland is removed, atrophy of the pancreas is observed, and the use of thyroid hormones leads to the restoration of its mass and structure.

The pancreas is a fairly active and powerful regulator of many biological reactions in the body, so any pathological and even functional changes in it always lead to varying degrees of severity of metabolic disorders. Changes in lipid metabolism, regardless of the underlying disease, are quite often associated with the so-called lipid triad: an increase in the level of triglycerides (TG), atherogenic low-density lipoproteins (LDL), and a decrease in high-density lipoproteins (HDL). This triad underlies the pathogenesis of many diseases and oxidative stress in general. [4]

Among the most frequent complications of hypothyroidism are also dyslipidemias, which are observed in most patients and lead to an increased risk of early development of atherosclerosis. Mechanisms of development of dyslipidemia in chronic pancreatitis and hy-